

Quality of Teachers and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Ondo State

Ehinola G.B¹

¹Department of educational management, faculty of education, adekunle ajasin university, akungba akoko, ondo state

Abstract: The study investigated the quality of teachers and academic performance of secondary school students in Ondo State. The study was designed to find out whether qualities of teachers; qualification and experience are related to academic performance. Descriptive survey designed was used. Proportionate random sampling technique was used to select 50 schools in Ondo state in which 50 principals and 150 teachers, teaching English language, mathematics, biology in the sampled schools. Two set of research instruments; Academic performance Questionnaire (APQ) for principals only; and Teachers Quality Questionnaire (TQQ) for teachers only were used for the study. Frequency counts and simple percentage was used to answer the research question while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient was used to analyze hypotheses tested. All hypotheses were tested at a significant level of 0.05. The study revealed the present quality of teacher in Ondo state. It also confirmed the significant relationship between the quality of teachers and student academic performance in the three core subjects; English language, (r-cal 0.501, r-tab 0.288) Mathematics 9r-cal 0,291, r-tab 0.288) and Biology (r-cal 0.484, r-tab 0.288) in Ondo State secondary schools. Suggestions were made that all unqualified teachers should be encouraged to obtain requisite qualification like Diploma in Education. Also more- in – service course, workshops, conferences, and seminars should be made available for the teachers and principals.

Keywords: Teachers' Quality, Academic Performance. Core subjects

Introduction

The success of any organization depends largely on the quality and strength of its staff. Ayodele (2000) opined that no matter how efficient and effective and administrator is, he hardly achieves success without the support and cooperation of well – qualified and dedicated staff. Quality of staff is the pivot and the determinant of education. A school without such caliber of staff may not be able to achieve the stated goals and objectives of education system.

According to Ibukun (2004) the politically motivated withdrawal of the Federal Government from the direct funding of secondary school system may have accounted to a largely extent, for the present inadequate supply of personnel. High quality of teachers are education's best resources and asset, the impact of adequate provision of human resource in terms of qualified teaching staff on the academic performance of student cannot be over emphasized.

Many research studies have indicated a shortage of teaching staff both in quality and quantity; in Nigeria, particularly in south western states (Oyo, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Lagos & Ekiti). Okunola (1985) in his various studies that focused on resources and performance in school have reported acute shortage and different forms of inadequacy in provision of teaching personnel in secondary schools.

Human resources is the vehicle of unity and progress that coordinate and move organization forward. The epic story of the creation of man and his responsibilities in Genesis 1 vs 29 God said ' I have given you every herb bearing seed, which is upon the face of all the earth and even trees' God has made man as the coordinator of all other resources for the benefit of all other institutions.

Human resources is necessary at all level of education but most needed at the secondary school level. Teachers are indispensable human resources in any educational system and the success of any educational planning and implementation to very large extent depends on teacher. Teachers are the pivot of implementation of all aspects of education and recognizing the vital role of teachers in the development of education. The Federal Government of Nigeria that, teacher education would continue to be given a major emphasis in the entire nation is education planning effort. This is because no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers FRN (2004), teachers are instrumental in translating content standards into teachable classrooms lessons. The teacher remains a constant factor in the successful implementation of educational programs. Obayan (2000), believed that teacher factor should be daily taken into

EHINOLA G.B (Correspondence)

gabrielehinola@yahoo.com

08059225814

consideration in educational programme. Musa (2004), opined that teacher holds the key to nation – building. The aspiration of any nation to transform into great country can only be possible if they are able and committed teacher to impact right knowledge, skill and attitude.

Teachers are the heartbeat of education in Nigeria. Ogunsaju (2000) was of the opinion that in any establishment be it school or cooperation, development of human resources are important tools for the survival of the formulation and successful implementation of educational policies in any country. Addressing the question what constitute quality teacher and quantity teacher. Satonwa (2003), identified subjective qualities as positive expectations, inspirational leadership and a wide representative of teaching skills and motivational strategies.

In Ondo State which is the focus of this study. According to the secondary teacher staff list as at Dec. 2006. Ondo State has 9,750 teaching staff out of which 2,047 were unqualified teachers. The total number of graduate teachers was 5,425 while NCE was 2,368 other 10. It is obvious that the population of unqualified teacher in the system is too high probably this is one of the factors responsible for poor academic performance of students in external examination conducted by West African Examination Council and National Examination Council in Nigeria.

Uwadia (2010) said 2009 result in WASSCE indicated a mass failure across the 36 states of nation and the Federal Capital Territory, for example Adamawa State recorded 0.08% pass in five subjects including English language and Mathematics. Akwa-Ibom State 0.05%; Bauchi State 0.29%; Borno State 0.05%, Kano State 0.24%, Kogi State 0.14%, Osun State 0.38%, Sokoto & Taraba States %, FCT Abuja 0.18% and Ondo State 0.95%.

Nwagun (1994) reported that inadequate supply of professionally qualifies teachers is one of the factors militating against students performance and this has given rise to the employment of non qualified teachers.

According to a survey released by the National Teacher Institute, more than 200, 000 teachers in this country are unqualified and this has great impact on the performance of students in their academic work. Abubakar (1993), expressed that teachers qualification is very important in determine the level of education. He regretted that falling standard of education may be attributed to a number of factors

among which is shortage of unqualified teachers in the school system. This argument was supported by Obiokor (1998) by attributing the falling standard in education to employment of non-professional qualified teachers who use the teaching profession as not only a stepping stone to other profession but also as a dumping ground for rejects in other fields and so they lack sense of commitment.

Abiodun (2005) observed that the teacher and his roles are perceived so important that, there is need to canvas legislation with ‘Punitive sanction’ for quack teachers while reviewing activity making his 100 days in office. He regretted the recent interest in teaching by non- professionals believing that the consequence could lead to decline in the nation’s educational sector. He said quackery is not restricted to teaching alone. It is however, more pathetic if it happen in academic.

Ula (1991) Abubakar (1993) and Ehinola (2009) have shown that a positive relationship exist between teachers quality and students performance. Therefore, this study wants to find out whether relationship exist between teachers quality and students performance especially in English Language, Mathematics and Biology.

Purpose of the Study

The study examine the extent and direction of relationship between teachers quality and academic performance of students in English Language, Mathematics and Biology.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria at large and particularly in Ondo State. Students’ performance in the external examination at secondary schools level is not encouraging. One of major causes of this mass failure could be shortage of professional and dedicated teaching staff in the educational system therefore this study want to know the current state of teachers quality in Ondo state and the relationship between teachers quality and academic performance of students in English Language, Mathematics and Biology.

In view of the above background and statement of the problem one research question was generated and three hypotheses were raised for the study.

Research Question

What is the present state of teacher quality in Ondo State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and students academic

- performance in English Language
- 2. There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and students academic performance in mathematics
- 3. There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and students academic performance in Biology

Methodology and Population

The survey type of design was used by the researcher to collect information that described the qualification of teacher teaching English language, Mathematics and Biology; and academic performance of students in three subjects. The population consisted of all senior secondary school principals and teachers in public secondary school in Ondo state.

Sample

For this study 50 senior secondary schools were selected for this study in which all the principals is those schools and 3 teachers teaching the three core subjects (English Language, Mathematics and

Biology) were selected from each school making a total of 150 teachers.

Instrument

Two instrument titled. Teachers Quality Questionnaire (TQQ) and Academic Performance Questionnaire (APQ). The teachers' Quality Questionnaire sought information about the quality of teachers; teachers qualification and teaching experience while Academic Performance Questionnaire (APQ) sought information on students' academic performance.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple percentage were used to answer the research question while the three hypotheses were tested by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient.

Result and Discussion

Research Question 1

What is the current quality of teachers in ondo state secondary school?

Table 1: Current Quality of Teacher in Ondo State secondary Schools.

Teachers Qualification	YEARS OF TEACHING EXPERIENCE									
	Less than 5 yrs		5-9 years		10-15 years		16 yrs above		Total sample	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
N.C.E	3	37.5	2	25	1	12.5	2	25	8	5.3
H.N.D	-	-	6	60	4	40	-	-	10	6.7
BA/Bsc	-	-	16	66.7	6	25	2	8.3	24	16
P.G.DE	-	-	5	16.1	6	19.4	20	64.5	31	20.7
BED/BA(ED) BSC. (ED)	8	13.3	17	28.3	18	30	17	28.3	60	40
M.ED	-	-	4	23.5	5	29.4	8	47.1	17	11.3
Total	11		50		40		49		150	100

The data presented in table shown that 8 (5.3%) of total sampled teachers had NCE of which 3 had less than 5 years working experience. In fact they are the recent non-teaching staff converted to teaching staff because of teaching qualification newly obtained at NCE level through Sandwich programmes. 10 (6.6%) of the teachers had Higher National Diploma of which non of them had less 5 years working experience, their experience range from 10 years and above. 24 (16%) of the teachers had BA/Bsc of which non of them had less than 5 years working experience .31 (20.7%) of the teachers had PGDE of which non of them had less than 5 years working experience. 60 (40%) of the teachers had B.ED/BA. (ED)/ B.SC(ED) of which 8 (13.3%) of them had less 5 years working experience, this is due to some of the non- teaching staff converted to teaching staff who had obtained Degree in Education through sandwich programmes. 52(87%) of them had 5 years an above

working experience. 17 (11.3%) of the teachers had Masters Degree in Education of which their working experiences ranged between 5 years and above.

From the table, polytechnic graduate and those from university without teaching qualification cannot be rightly perceived as quality teachers. These crops of teaching staff are 34 (22.7%) of the group. In deed knowledge of subject matter, however, important should be matched with adequate training in the methodology, philosophy, psychology and foundational concepts of teaching the subject. it is therefore not total surprising that products of the school were not performing well in their final examination.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and student academic performance in English language.

Table 2:

Quality of teachers and students academic performance in English Language

Variable	N	r-cal	r-tab
Teachers' Quality	50	0.501	0.288
Academic performance in English language	50		

P<0.05

The result in table 2 indicate that r-calculated (0.501) is greater than v-table (0.288) at P<0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shown that there was significant relationship between teachers' quality and students' academic performance in English Language

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and students academic performance in Mathematics.

Table 3: Quality of teachers and students academic performance in Mathematics

Variable	N	r-cal	r-tab
Teachers' Quality	50	0.291	0.288
Academic performance in English language	50		

P<0.05

The result in table 3 indicates that r-calculated (0.291) is greater than r-table (0.288) at P<0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between teachers' quality and students' academic performance in Mathematics.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between quality of teacher and students academic performance in Biology.

Tables 3: Quality of teacher and students academic performance in Biology

Variable	N	r-cal	r-tab
Teachers' Quality	50	0.484	0.288
Academic performance in English language	50		

P<0.05

The result in table 4 reveal that r-calculated (0.484) is greater than r-table (0.288) at P<0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between teachers' quality and students' academic performance in Biology.

teacher factors and years of experience among others to be consistently related to students' academic performance. Marrianhill (1979) support this study that utilization of unqualified and under qualified educators in South Africa impact negatively on the quality of teaching with its implication on performance. Hence, the quality of the teachers thus exerts great influence on the quality of educational output. Therefore, teacher could be described as indispensable human resources and in fact, the most important factor in the school system.

Discussion

The result of this study indicated that there is a significant relationship between teachers' quality and academic performance(r-cal. 501, r – table 0.288). This study has also shown that positive relationship exist between teachers' quality and students' performance. This is in agreement with Ukeje (1991) that there is direct relationship between the teachers' quality and academic performance. He attributes some of the defects of the present educational system to the poor quality of teachers. Fuller and clark (2000) have also found that students' performance was associated with class preparation, time and experience. Hanushek (2001) studies

The finding in table 3 shown that there is a significant relationship between teachers' quality and performance of students in mathematics. There was a shortage or non availability of mathematic qualified teachers. It was discover that some of graduate teachers in secondary schools were unqualified. If there is positive relationship between teacher quality and performance in Mathematics the shortage of teachers for this vital subject perhaps explain the

dismal performance of students in Ondo State and possibly in Nigeria in general. Fagbulu (1992) had opined that in any formal human learning situation, a teacher is indispensable. This reinforces the importance of qualified teachers in secondary schools cannot be over emphasized especially in a core subject like mathematics.

The finding in table 4 shown that there is a significant relationship between teacher' quality and performance of students in the subject. This could be attributed to the importance of qualified teachers in Biology. This result corroborated Comber and Keeves (1973) Observation that year of experience of secondary Education science teacher correlated significantly with students achievement especially in Biology. Also, Fafunwa (1974) is of the opinion that shortage of teachers may bring about poor performance of students. He commented on the importance of qualified teachers for the purpose of better academic performance. Also, Bajah (1979) discovered that teachers and facilities influenced students' performance.

Reference

- 1) Abiodun F. (2005): Provost Prescribes Positive Sanction For Quack Teachers. Guardian Thursday November, 17th
- 2) Abubakar I. (1993): Education Today: A Quarterly Journal of Education. Federal Ministry of Education, Vol. 4: No 4 Pg 105-107.
- 3) Ehinola G.B (2009): Resource Availability and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Ondo State. Ph.D Thesis. Adekunle Ajasin University Akungba.
- 4) Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004): National Policy on Education (Revised) Minimum Standard for NCE Teachers 4th Edition.
- 5) Ibukun W.O (2004): Educational Management: Theory and Practices (2nd Edition) Greenline Publishers, Lagos.
- 6) Musa H.B (2004) Preface to teachers Code of Conduct, Teachers Registration country Nigeria.
- 7) Nwagwu C.C (1984): Academic and National Preference of Nigerian Secondary School Student: A challenge to Policy Maker Journal of Vocation Education and Training 50 (1) 113-122.
- 8) Obayan PAI (2000): UBE as Living Reality. The Question of Sustainability National Stakeholder Consultation on Education Abuja.
- 9) Obiokor O.C (1998): The Falling Standard of Education Respectively. New Nigeria Newspaper June, 12th.
- 10) Ogunsaju S. (2000): Human Resource Development and Productivity. Education and Productivity in Nigeria. In Fagbemiye E.O and Durosaro, D.O A publication of The Nigeria Association for Educational Administration And Planning, Unilorin.
- 11) Okunola, p.O (1985): Resources Utilization and Projections in Secondary Education in Oyo State, Nigeria Unpublished Ph.D Thesis. University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- 12) Oni, J.O. (1992): Resources and Utilization as Correlates of School Academic Performance in the Secondary Pre-Vocational Education in Ogun State. Unpublished Ph.d Thesis. University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- 13) Sotonwa, O.O (2003) Quality of Teacher and Quality Teaching Towards Achieving Quality in Universal Basic Education. Nigeria Journal of Educational Research and Education (4) 1: 67-78.
- 14) TESCOM, (2006). Teaching Staff List, Akure Global Press.
- 15) Ukeje, B.O. (1991). Educational Administration fourth Dimension Enugu, Fourth Dimension Press.
- 16) Uwadiae, I. (2010): WAEC records 75% failure in English and Mathematics. The nation, August 15th, 2010, page 1 and 24.